

MIRRI-ERIC Policy on Biorisk Assessment and Biosecurity Measures

Effective Biosecurity risk management is more than reliable and appropriate risk assessment. It also involves assigning responsibilities to members of staff and communication to (internal) staff and third parties (users). In this context awareness raising is the most fundamental basis for implementation of biosecurity and requires educational programs in the future in order to communicate broadly what biosecurity is and why biosecurity measures are demanded. MIRRI's policy will capture this and also address the issue in its training and education offer.

The key elements of the MIRRI-ERIC policy on biorisk management in mBRCs

1. Follow the relevant national law
 - a. adhere to the Code of Conduct on Biosecurity for BRCs
 - b. other comparable recognized standards
 - c. OECD Best Practice Guidelines on Biosecurity for BRCs
2. Follow the development of biosecurity implementation strategies and adjust practice accordingly;
3. Work in collaboration with MIRRI-ERIC and external partners towards developing and implementing protocols for adequate biosecurity risk assessment of holdings and normative compliance in MIRRI-mBRCs;
4. Offer available specific expertise to the MIRRI biosecurity expert cluster;
5. Work with national authorities to increase competence and advocate the establishment of national biosecurity offices and their international cooperation;
6. Work in collaboration with MIRRI-ERIC and external partners to strengthen the ethical basis for biosecurity in the scientific community;
7. Adopt existing or develop new educational tools to raise awareness among mBRC staff.